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Impact of Tourism for Socio-Economic Development of Nepal

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Introduction of Tourism :-

- Tourism refers to the trips that involve travelling of people outside the place of their residence or work for leisure; pleasure; vacation; business; study; observing new places, culture, living activities and other purposes.
- Tourism is an important source of income.
- Nowadays, it is considered as an industry.
- Tourism is important for the growth and development of a developing country like Nepal.
- In a wider concept, People believe that tourism is a service industry that takes care of visitors when they are away from home.
- Different festivals organized by different destinations like Pokhara Street Festival-2003, Baglung Festival-2060, Sauraha Year-2060, Ghale Gaon Festival-2003 and many others are the examples of the local peoples' interest in tourism promotion from both domestic and international importance which not only accelerates business activities but popularizes the identity of the place. It justifies the day by day increasing interest of people in tourism development around their area.
- Accommodations, food and beverage Services, recreation and entertainment, transportation and travel services are the main areas of Tourism in Nepal.
- Mountain climbing, trekking, paragliding, rafting, bungee jumping, mountain flight, rock climbing, mountain biking, jungle safari, rock climbing, bird watching, and sightseeing are the major tourism activities in Nepal.

Prospectus of Tourism in Nepal :-

- There are huge possibilities of expansion of tourism in Nepal.

- Here are some glimpses of prospectus of tourism in Nepal
- Nepal is a country full of Natural beauties like Mount Everest, interesting caves, rare animals, dense and green forest, waterfalls, lakes, etc. These natural heritages have proved to be a natural blessing to Nepal. Their development and protection help to develop tourism in Nepal.
- There are some places of historical and religious importance which are our religious or cultural heritages. Nepal is a holy place for Hindus as well as Buddhists and so on. Pashupati Temple, Krishna Temple, Janaki Temple, etc are Hindus temples. Nepal is also the birthplace of Gautam Buddha. And there are other religious and historical places where tourists want to visit Nepal either for religious purposes or for study and research about these places.
- Nepal is a multi-ethnic, nation with over 60 different ethnic groups living in different parts of the country. There live 125 castes or communities people, they speak about 131 languages. Each caste and ethnic group have their own language, culture, way of living, etc. This cultural diversity attracts the tourists to study and enjoy with them.
- Nepal is rich in biodiversity. In Nepal, there are various places, where different varieties of wild animals, plants are found. All these provide an additional attraction to tourists to visit Nepal.
- The cost of living in Nepal is very low in comparison to other countries. Therefore, it is a suitable place for tourists in different countries and different status and stays for a long duration at a very low cost.
- There are various unique recreational places for enjoyment for tourists. Tourists always want to visit such places.
- There are other prospects of tourism

industries such as ancient art and culture, suitable climate, birthplaces of brave persons, mountainous areas, etc.

Impacts of Tourism :-

- Tourism has various impacts like socio-economic, socio-cultural, environmental, political etc.
- Here we discuss only about the socio-economic impacts of tourism in Nepal
- There are positive and negative both types of socio-economic impacts of tourism in Nepal. They are elaborated here.

Positive Social Impacts of Tourism :-

- ❖ Tourism is an important medium of cultural exchange. Due to tourism development, people from different countries come to Nepal, which helps to exchange art and culture between Nepal and the rest of the world. It helps us to change the traditional concept and introduce modern thinking and others.
- ❖ Many tourists are often coming to visit and learn about various Nepalese cultures. Tourists visit Baglung to learn more about the Magar culture. Tourists visit Chitwan to learn more about Tharu Culture etc. Many other destinations will make an effort to preserve and protect the local culture.
- ❖ Tourism requires many facilities and infrastructures to meet the needs of the tourist. So, local people gained new roads, new playgrounds, bus services etc. as a result of tourism. This can provide a great boost to their quality of life.
- ❖ Various Museums and galleries are established as a commercialization of local culture and arts which help to promote and preserve local traditions and strengthen the economic condition of the community.
- ❖ Some destinations are encouraging local cultures and arts to be revitalized. This may be in the form of museum exhibitions, in the way that restaurants and shops are

decorated.

- ❖ Many tourists visit the destinations like Bhaktapur, Kirtipur, Lalitpur specially to see local heritages. Due to this, we have efforts to preserve local heritages.

Positive Economic Impacts of Tourism :-

- Tourism plays a crucial role in the economic development of Nepal.
- Some positive economic impacts of tourism include increasing tax revenue and personal income, changing in the living standard of people, increasing in social facilities, promotion in trade and business, increasing more employment opportunities and publicity of nation etc.
- It is the major source of foreign currency earnings.
- Tourism helps to generate employment opportunities directly or indirectly to the people in different tourism-related activities such as in hotels, trekking, traveling, mountaineering business, etc.
- The development of the handicraft industry also depends on the development of tourism. Tourists are interested in buying handicraft goods which represent Nepalese art and culture.
- Expansion and development of tourism would help to develop backward areas because most of the tourist destinations are in remote areas.
- Tourism is also a source of government revenue; the government earns income from tourism activities. Such as hotel and restaurant tax, bars tax, visa fee, airport tax, etc. This increases government revenue. In 2018 AD, the contribution of tourism in GDP of Nepal is 2.1%, 1.6% in 2019 and 0.2% in 2020 AD. It is decreased due to the pandemic Covid-19.
- In addition, the local economy is stimulated and diversified, goods are manufactured more locally, and new markets open for local business owners to expand due to Tourism.

Negative Social Impacts of Tourism :-

- Tourism can affect the lifestyle and livelihood of the native people. It also affects the normal life of local people. It means local residents are more likely to mimic tourists and follow their way of living. Nowadays Nepalese people are blindly following western customs, cultures, languages, dress-ups, and festivals due to foreign influence. And it has threatened the local people's beliefs, festivals, lifestyles, languages, etc.
- There are many changes that come about as a result of tourism which are not desirable. Changing in the way of speaking, dressing; depending upon only tourism and leaving native activities like farming etc. are the changes due to Tourism.
- We are losing our individuality and gaining a sense of 'global being'.
- Globalization is inevitable in tourism because of the interaction between tourists and hosts, which typically come from different geographic and cultural backgrounds.
- Some tourists give chocolates or sweets to the children of their destination. Slowly, it changes the habits of these children. Foods like pizza, burger, and cornflakes are the impacts of tourism.
- There are differences in culture between tourists and local peoples. So, these differences may bring in cultural shocks and clashes resulting in tourist satisfaction.
- All the people coming from the globe might not be innocent. Such people visit places in order to spread violence, supply drugs and to cause other various problems. Many tourists travel to poach animals, rob idols from the temples and to do various illegal and unethical acts. Social problem like Girl trafficking, kidnapping, drugs abuse, poaching animals, terrorism, rape are increasing due to tourism.
- Crime rates typically increase with the growth of mass tourism. The presence of a large number of tourists with a lot of money

to spend and often carrying valuable things like cameras and jewellery increases the attraction for criminals and brings the activities like robbery and drug dealing.

- Gambling is a common occurrence as a result of tourism. Growth of casinos and other gambling facilities can encourage not only the tourists to part with their cash, but also the local population.
- Tourists are given more preference by the government and other local bodies. In the name of their accommodation, they are given high qualities of food and water. It doesn't cause any side effects in urban and developed areas but it boosts problems in rural areas where there is not adequate food and water. It causes scarcity of food and water in the rural or deprived areas.
- Tourism areas like Sagarmatha Base Camp, Kathmandu valley and other areas are being polluted day by day. So we can say that tourism can pollute and destroy our natural resources and tourist areas.
- Due to the flow of the huge crowd in cultural and natural heritage, it might damage the beauty and their importance. If it is not managed properly then it won't be surprising to see such heritage being converted into dumping trash.
- There is a high risk of disease transmission like Covid-19 due to tourism.

Negative Economic Impacts of Tourism :-

- Tourist destinations are much more expensive than the other ones. It means the overall price of living is more expensive in all aspects of such places. Due to tourism the price of land, houses, rent, goods and other stuff get hiked which might be a problem to local and poor residents there.
- There is seasonal tourism in Nepal. Tourists' inflow in the high season is high and in the low season is low. So people get a sound job in high seasons but they remain jobless in the low seasons. This may lead such jobless people to do illegal and easy money jobs.

- Due to the tourism, the areas become crowded and impact that resources become unsustainable and exhausted, the carrying capacity for tourists in a destination site may be depleted.
- Tourism can raise property values near the tourism area, effectively pushing out locals and encouraging businesses to migrate inwards to encourage and take advantage of more tourist spending.
- Due to the tourism, the demonstration effect is seen on local communities of Nepal. The local inhabitants copy the behavioral patterns of tourists. Locals copy the consumption patterns to improve their social status. Tourism has also been accused of affecting social behavior of the younger members of a host community, who may imitate what tourists do, impacting traditional value systems.

Like these there are so many other positive and negative impacts of tourism in Nepal.

Conclusion :- In conclusion, I want to say that we have to struggle first with pandemic Covid-19. Then we should launch the best and long term policy for development of tourism which helps to decrease the negative impacts and increase the positive impacts of tourism and becomes the milestone in the development of tourism in Nepal.

Impact of Tourism for Socio-Economic Development of Nepal

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Abstract :- Nepal is a country situated between India and China, which is a part of Asia. Nepal lies in the mountain ranges of the Himalayas. Mount Everest (8848) the highest peak in the world, is in Nepal region and birth place Buddha in Nepal, so many tourism is becoming an important industry of Nepal. That is so, tourism industry is helpful for socio-Economics development of Nepal.

Introduction :- Nepal a Country lies between the latitudes 26° N and 30° N and between the longitudes 80° E And approximately. The total area of Nepal is about 1,41,000 sq.kilometers ,Nepal is a land-locked country ,surrounded by mountain ranges, of the Himalayas .There are number of ranges in Nepal. The parts north of central Nepal are the highest 8848M. hilly regions in the world mountain Everest is the highest peak in the world and all the rivers in Nepal have their sources in Himalaya so, number of tourist is coming to visit the highest peak in Nepal . Natural's climate is also delightful ,The climate in the Katmandu basin in central Nepal is warm in summer and cold in winter and Lumbini is the birth place of Gautama Buddha that is why the tourist is attracting, like that pleasurable country Nepal . We can called ,the Nepal developed Economically and socially because of tourism industry is also developed in Nepal ,that is why tourism is the pack bone of country Nepal and its development.

1) **Socio-Economic condition of the Nepal :-** A majority of the people in Nepal are yellow –skinned like China but not heighted .They depending upon the deciduous forests, Goats, sheep, yaks and horses likes domestic animals. Nepali is the depending upon Agriculture which has very little cultivable, main occupation of the people is agriculture ; There are also mica mines, the main mineral of Nepal, In the Nepal, there are also very few industries, like minerals, power resources

and technology ; However , there are also a few agro based industries ,carpet making ,weaving woolen cloth and handloom cloth , tanning leather ,rice and oil mills, lumbering ,rope and basket making etc also important industries of Nepal which helpful solve the economical problems. But tourism is the main instrument for socio –Economic development and solve the socio economic problems of Nepal culture life of the Nepalian people like the Indian people mainly with Hindu, Buddhist, and Muslims the Gurkhas in Nepal.

2) **For Tourism, Transport and communication is too much important tools :-** Nepal country is surrounding of Himalaya ,the hilly nature .So, transports is very difficult , and everyone knows that in the tourism industries Transports and communication is the most important factors. There are roads to facilitate transport in the plain areas but in hilly area the yak, a animal is the only means of transport in inaccessible areas.

Katmandu is the capital city of Nepal, the highway from Katmandu to Raxaul on the Indian border is known Tribhuvan Rajpeth highways and another highway is the Siddhartha highway connecting pokra to Sonali is also on the Indian border. The way of transport is so much important in tourism and socio-Economic development, Travel & Tourism creates also drives exports and generates prosperity across the world, that also created the jobs and others to napoleons and GDP also developed by transport and tourism industries. Tourism has provided employment to local people also, although it provided 10 lakh jobs around in Nepal, Similar effect of tourism can be observed on trade, other Industries and local development also that the important tool like transport and communication.

3) **Analysis and Discussion economic and social development of Tourism in Nepal** :- Tourism Industry of Nepal has become a major source of service industry which has also provided ,in large scale of employment ,and originated valuable foreign exchange which is also Nepal economic back –bone and has been in five year development plan(1997-2002). Tourism industry also figures consistently among the largest provider of chargeable currency Gross Domestic product (G.D.P.) is developed that help to losing the poorlity.

Tourism has become a vital source for the economic development that help the development of poor peoples and social life of Nepal, unemployed people also become the employment that's provided the Tourism. Tourism provides employment to many people directly as well as indirectly and creates a wide range of jobs which extend from unskilled to theand various hotel, taxi driver, tourist guide etc.

Tourism has also impact on the domestic, as well as international trade. According to the choice and demand of tourists develop the trade of handicraft, curios, souvenir and other produced locally and globally both are available in the tourist centers. For tourism to provide better services and hospitality the government including the Ngo invests into infrastructure like rails, road, hotels, communications, electricity, local people also to develop himself & socially & educationally development of Nepali & Nepal as a Country.

Conclusion :- Nepal is very diverse in socio-economic and physical futures, in the age of modern era where the whole world is marching towards modernization and globalization, Nepal still has preserved its old culture and traditions. But the available natural condition highest mountain areas & natural climate & natural glories & Lumbini the birth place of Buddha are attracted the tourist of the world. So, Nepal developed the tourism industries Upon that the

tourism that change the life of Nepal.

Because of tourism developed in Nepal the economic condition of the Nepali people Also developed that affected to developed the social culture & educationally life of Nepali people. In short, Nepal is in surrounding the hill area but and that is why the Nepal country is also helped that climate which developed the tourism.

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Tourism and Economy

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Abstract :- Tourism is one of the fastest growing economic sectors and is an important driver to enhance economic growth. Tourism contributes towards complete growth and development of any country. For many developed and developing countries, the tourism sector is a major source of employment, government revenue and foreign exchange earnings. Sustainable tourism is a major tool for development and poverty alleviation in developing countries. All of us know that tourism leads to employment diversification on a local level, which reduces the poverty and helps in economic development at local level, state level and country level. Before COVID-19, travel and tourism had become one of the most important sectors in jobs and the world economy. Unfortunately tourism dependent countries have negative impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic. Tourism and travel sectors are disproportionately affected by the COVID-19 pandemic and will continue to struggle until people feel safe to travel again with rules and regulations. It is too early to determine how long the people will take time to feel safe to travel. Tourism boosts the the economy, creates thousands of jobs, develops the infrastructures of a country, and plants a sense of cultural exchange between foreigners and citizens. The number of jobs created by tourism in many different areas is significant

Keywords :- Tourism, Sustainable, Poverty, Employment, Economy.

Introduction :- This paper presents that tourism sector is significant for economy. In India tourism has become one of the major sectors of the economy, and contributing to an employment opportunities. Tourism is one of the fastest growing services with expansion and diversification. Tourism plays a major role in development of economic status of any country. It helps significantly to the country for creating

the employment opportunities to the large number of people. Moreover, it is also one of the important issues to attract more foreign exchanges (Vijayaragavan, T.2014). Medical tourism, Wellness tourism, Adventure tourism, Heritage tourism, Eco tourism, rural tourism, Wildlife tourism, Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions tourism are important main types of tourism. Tourism tends to encourage the development of infrastructure that benefits the host community, including various means of transports, health care facilities, in addition to the hotels and restaurants for visitors. The development of infrastructure has in turn induced the development of other directly productive activities. In most of the tourism expenditures are in "Accommodation, food and services" (B.N. Gopalakrishnan, et.al. 2020). Tourism can also help to promote peace and stability in developing country like India by providing jobs, generating income, diversifying the economy, and promoting cross-cultural awareness (Honey and Gilpin 2009).

Objective :- Objectives of the Study is to understand the opportunities in tourism, to aware different forms of tourism, to identify the challenges involved tourism and to know the Positive impacts of Tourism.

Methodology :- Survey of literature was done. Interaction with persons of different economic status and thought was done.

Result and Discussion :- Challenges in Tourism are physical infrastructure such as ports transport to urban infrastructure such as roads, electricity, water supply, sewerage, common facilities and tale communication. The sectors related to the travel and tourism industry include airlines, surface transport, accommodation (hotels, guest houses), and hospitality and facilitation systems, among others. Facilities like air, rail, road

connectivity, and hospitality services are still need to be improved to connect various cities across the country. This remains a major issue for the development of tourism. Tourists largely depends on road network at local level rather other mode.

Despite of numerous efforts to modernize the road facilities connectivity remains a major challenge. There is a great need to improve transportation facilities to connect various locations across different regions in the country. The basic amenities such as drinking water, well maintained and clean waiting rooms and toilets, first aid, cafeteria, and parking facilities are required. Inadequate infrastructure facilities affect tourism and also lead to an

increase in the outflow of domestic tourists to other competitive neighboring countries. To sustain growth in the tourism industry trained manpower is required at various levels such as skilled managers and skilled supervisors. Shortage of tourism training infrastructure, qualified trainers, and lack of proper strategies and policies for human resource development also affect tourism. India has a lot of interest among the tourists in the world and of course the officials in the field of tourism have a high income from this industry which is sure to attract more investment in the Indian tourism industry in the coming years (Goutam, 2018). Tourism is an activity which brings the consumers to the producers (T.A. Williams et.al. 1979).

Table 1 Important Reason for Tourism

S. No.	Tourism
1	Wellness tourism
2	Adventure tourism
3	Medical tourism
4	Heritage tourism
5	Eco tourism
6	Wildlife tourism
7	Rural tourism
8	Conferences
9	Meetings
10	Exhibitions tourism and more.

Table 2 Challenges in Tourism

S. No.	Challenges
1	Connectivity of roads , Trains, Flights etc
2	Electricity
3	Water supply,
4	Common facilities
5	Language problem
6	Telecommunication
7	Sanitation
8	Availability of Food (Veg. / Non Veg.)
9	Common sense
10	Tourist must be Environment friendly
11	Accommodation
12	Trained and skilled manpower

Taken altogether, the availability and accessibility of transportation will have an impact on the financial recovery of tourism and dependent economy. Many predictions do not anticipate a return to normal levels in the short term for the tourism sector. Moreover, it is also one of the important issues to attract more foreign exchanges. In tourism sector there must be no gap between demand and supply with respect to manpower and other facilities for upliftment of economy. We need to concentrate to have liberal policies, relaxation in taxes, comprehensive package and so on to influence tourist and foreign investment. There is also a need to increase the government's role to make flourish in tourism and established in the global market. of course India has been launched the Incredible India to make tourism better. Tourism has become the world's largest industry, generating wealth and employment, opening the minds of both visitors and the visited to different ways of life.

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Compulsory Marriage Registration : An Overview

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Abstract :- Marriage registration is an essential step in Indian society. Increasing problems in the society, malpractices like- child marriage, illegal marriage, fraud in marriage etc considering serious matters, the Supreme Court on February 14, 2006, has made the 'Registration of Marriage Compulsory' in all the states to facilitate meeting the challenges in future. As a result of increasing abandonment situation in the society, increase in divorce, separation etc., registration of marriage is becoming more necessary. Relationships have their own special importance in Indian society and this mutual relationship is its fundamental identity, but in today's present era, when our country is moving step by step from developing to developed, our society does not think of marriage without religious rituals and band-baaja-baraat. The way marriage is considered important in the society, in the same way, to tie it in an unbreakable bond and to maintain the security of marriage in future and to avoid the upcoming challenges, marriage registration is an extremely necessary step for which the society needs to be aware. What they do not know is that in today's modern lifestyle, the registration of marriage is more important than the celebration of marriage and the marriage will be considered legally certified only through the marriage registration.

Introduction :- Since independence, numerous initiatives have been taken to address the issue of gender inequality. Reform initiatives taken so far have succeeded to a large extent, however, child marriages, bigamy and gender violence continue to persist in our society, despite legislations prohibiting and penalising such practices.¹ Several disputes are pending before the courts regarding matrimonial status of the parties.² Women are often denied the status of wife due to absence of record proving a valid marriage. The courts have time and again emphasised on making registration of marriage compulsory, to prevent denial of status to women and to children born

out of wedlock.³

Instances of marriage fraud have also come to light in recent times. In the absence of compulsory registration, women are duped into marrying without performance of the conditions of a valid marriage. This deprives women of societal recognition and legal security. Such fraudulent marriages are especially on rise among non-resident Indians.⁴ Compulsory registration can serve as a means to ensure that conditions of a valid marriage have been performed.

The Births, Deaths and Marriages Registration Act, 1886 provided for voluntary registration of births and deaths only for certain classes of people and also made a provision for effective registration of marriages under the Indian Christian Marriages Act, 1872 and the Parsi Marriage and Divorce Act 1936.

While provisions for registration exist under various laws- such as the Hindu Marriages Act, 1955, the Special Marriages Act, 1954, the Parsi Marriages and Divorce Act, 1936 and the Indian Christian Marriages Act, 1872, however, there is no provision that provides for simply keeping a record of all marriages and is available to any and every individual in the country regardless of religion, region or customs.

Background :- India signed the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) on 30 June 1980 and ratified it on 9 July 1993. After that India was expected to submit its report to the CEDAW. The first report was submitted in 1998. The combined fourth and fifth periodic reports were submitted in 2012. The Committee, in its concluding observations on this report in the year 2014, in Para 39, urged India to speedily enact legislation 'to require compulsory registration of all marriages and simultaneously requested to consider to withdraw its declaration

to Article 16 (2) of the Convention'. Article 16 of the Convention pertains to "Equality in marriage and family relations". The Committee has expressed its concern in para 40 about the co-existence of multiple legal systems with regard to marriage and family relations in India which apply to the different religious groups and which results in the deep and persistent discrimination against women.

In 2006, the Supreme Court in *Seema v. Ashwani Kumar & ors.*⁶ observed that 'Marriages of all persons who are citizens of India belonging to various religions should be registered compulsorily in their respective States, where the marriage is solemnised'. Further, as and when the Central Government enacts a comprehensive Statute, the same shall be placed before the Court for scrutiny. The judgment also referred to the Bill produced by the National Commission of Women.

This Report proposes to amend the Registration of Births and Deaths Act, 1969 to include the compulsory registration of marriages within its purview. In brief, it marriage includes marriage solemnised between a couple belonging to any caste or religion or tribe under any law or custom or usage in any form or manner recognised by law or marriage registered under any law including re-marriage.

Registration of marriage would in fact, help in better implementation of already existing laws that aim at preventing child marriage et al. It would also aid in eliminating practices such early and forced marriages.⁶ It can be helpful in achieving gender equality and empowering women.

The recommendation is not aimed at eliminating diversity of personal laws and instead accepts prevailing customs/ or personal laws concerning solemnisation of marriage; provided that these marriages are registered under the Compulsory Registration of Births Deaths and Marriages Registration Act or any other law for the tinier being in force in the State. The report

does not aim to nullify the existing provisions for registration of marriages under different state laws.

Marriage Registration: A Global Overview :-

United Nations has recognised the importance of creating a record of vital events such as birth, death and marriage. Creation of such a civil registry for citizens serves the purpose of creating a legal document that could be used to protect and establish rights of individuals. This also results in the creation of a database that contains vital statistics of important and relevant life events. The United Nations defines civil registration as:⁷

The continuous, permanent, compulsory and universal recording of the occurrence and characteristics of vital events pertaining to the population as provided through decree or regulation in accordance with the legal requirements of a country. Civil registration is carried out primarily for the purpose of establishing the legal documents required by law. These records are also a main source of vital statistics. Complete coverage, accuracy and timeliness of civil registration are essential to ensure the quality of vital statistics.

In the Indian context however, the maintenance of vital statistics does not serve the sole purpose of record-keeping by the State. In many ways it enables social legislations to be effectively enforced. In certain countries there is also a specific register relating to registrations specifically of 'family' events.

This register has been termed as 'family album', 'household register' et al in various countries. In many countries the official recognition of one's status or of family-related events such as marriage is only granted when all such events have been reported and registered in the family or civil register. For instance Japan considers a marriage to be legally effective only when the household register is updated with the knowledge of the event- this is known as *Koseki*. In other countries however, such registers work

as centralised repositories for family events that would have legal repercussions which include births, deaths, marriages and even expatriations, as is the case in Germany where the register is known by the name familienbuch and France, where it is called livret de famille. However, this is not the sole source of official recognition for such events.

Registration of marriage is not compulsory in all countries. However, most countries recognise the need for such registration.

In South Africa, laws of marriage are laid down in Marriage Act, 1961. The non-registration does not affect the validity of the marriage and marriage can be registered postnuptially. While, a duly signed marriage certificate serves as prima facie proof of the existence of the marriage, the existence of the marriage may still be proved by other evidence. Similarly, Section 8 of the Australian Marriage Act, 1961 provides for registration of marriages.

The Muslim Marriages and Divorce Registration Act, 1974 of Bangladesh also provides a complete procedure by which all marriages solemnised should be registered and non-registration is punishable with simple imprisonment which may extend up to two years, or fine up to 3000 Taka, or with both.⁸

In Pakistan, every marriage solemnised under the Muslim law is required to be registered compulsorily under the Muslim Family Law Ordinance, 1961. After passing of the Hindu Marriage Bill, in March 2017, even the Hindus in Pakistan are required to get their marriages registered.

In Turkey, there is no specific law on registration of marriage but the marriage is concluded only through civil ceremony in front of the Registrar. This requirement flows from the Turkish Civil Code enacted in 1926 which was amended by Turkish Civil Code (2001).

In Indonesia, Article 2 para 2 of the

Marriage Law of 1974 provides for compulsory registration of marriages. In Sri Lanka, under Muslim Marriage and Divorce Act, 1951 (promulgated on 1-8-1954) marriages solemnised therein are required to be registered compulsorily under section 17 of the said Act.⁹

The requirement of celebrating and registering a marriage before a public authority and certificate of marriage as the only admissible means of proof of marriage is also available in the Civil Codes of various countries, for example :-

- French Civil Code - Arts.165 to 169.
- Italian Civil Code - Arts. 106, 107 & 130.
- Civil Code of Brazil - Arts.1533 and 1534.
- Portuguese Civil Code of 1966 - Arts.1615, 1616, 1651 & 1653.
- Civil Code of Quebec - Arts.365 & 378.

Indian Legislative Framework :- In India, not recognising unregistered marriage as a valid would be highly unsuitable, as many marriages commonly take place informally in gatherings of relatives, with or without presence of priests, or in any other customary manner which must also be recognised as valid. It was for this reason that, like various other countries, India also expressed its reservation even while ratifying the Convention of 1993. Customary practices are so prolific and personal law systems also prevail making it necessary for the law to accept cultural and regional diversity. Therefore the idea is to encourage legal education among the people, so that these ceremonies can be preceded or succeeded by registration of the event.

An unregistered marriage is not to be treated as 'void' but simply in an attempt to encourage registration, there can be small penalties attached to non-registration. This would help in a circumstance when the spouse has been left destitute and a second marriage has been contracted by the other spouse, the proof of first marriage will be indisputable and not permit a spouse to abandon his family and maintenance obligations etc.

➤ **Existing Central Legislation on Registration/Compulsory Registration of Marriages and Divorces :-**

- The Indian Christian Marriage Act, 1872
- The Kazis Act 1880
- The Anand Marriage Act, 1909
- The Farsi Marriage and Divorce Act, 1936
- The Special Marriage Act, 1954
- The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955
- The Foreign Marriage Act 1969

➤ **Developments in States and Union Territories in India :-** Pursuant to the directions/ observations of the Supreme Court in *Seema v. Ashwani Kumar* many states have passed law or framed rules for compulsory registration of marriages, i.e.

A. Compulsory Registration of Marriages Acts:

1. The Punjab Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act, 2012 provides for compulsory registration of marriages solemnised within the State under any law governing the parties irrespective of their religion, caste, creed or nationality.
2. The Delhi (Compulsory Registration of Marriage) Order, 2014 extends to all marriages solemnised in Delhi irrespective of cast creed and religion professed by the parties to the marriage.
3. The Haryana Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act 2008 provides for compulsory registration of marriages solemnised within the State, irrespective of caste, religion and creed and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.
4. The Meghalaya Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act 2012 provides for compulsory registration of marriages solemnised in the State of Meghalaya and for matters connected therewith; amended by the Meghalaya Compulsory Registration of Marriages (Amendment) Act, 2015.
5. The Uttarakhand Compulsory Registration of Marriage Act, 2010 provides for the compulsory registration of all marriages solemnised in the State of Uttarakhand so as

to prevent child marriages, check bigamy or polygamy, help women to exercise their rights of maintenance from husband and custody of children, enable widows to claim inheritance and to serve as deterrent to husbands deserting their wives and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto.

6. The Tamil Nadu Registration of Marriages Act, 2009. "Marriage" includes all marriages solemnised by persons belonging to any caste or religion under any law for the time being in force, or as per any custom or usage in any form or manner and also includes remarriage. As per Section 3 of the Act Marriages to be compulsorily registered. It reads:

Marriages to be compulsorily registered :- Every marriage performed on and from the date of commencement of this Act shall be registered under this Act notwithstanding the fact that the said marriage had been entered in the marriage registers governed by any other personal laws of the parties to the marriage or custom or usage or tradition).

- (i) Similarly, Rajasthan too has enacted the Rajasthan Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act, 2009, wherein it is provided for Compulsory Registration of Marriages of citizens of India solemnised in the State.
- (ii) The Mizoram Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act, 2007 provides for compulsory registration of marriages solemnised in the State of Mizoram, "marriage" includes all the marriages contracted by persons belonging to any caste, tribe or religion, and the marriages contracted as per any custom, practice or tradition, and also includes re-marriages.
- (iii) Further there are the Karnataka Marriages (Registration and Miscellaneous Provisions) Act, 1976, (3) The Himachal Pradesh Registration of Marriages Act, 1996, and (4) The Andhra Pradesh Compulsory Registration of Marriages Act, 2002.
- (iv) In Odisha, the registration of marriages were

regulated under various Acts and Rules; namely, (i) the Orissa Mohammedan Marriages and Divorces Registration Act, 1949 and Rules, 1976 for Muslim Community (Section-8 and Rule 2A) (ii) the Orissa Hindu Marriage Registration Rules, 1960 (Rules-4, 4A and 4B) (iii) the Indian Christian Marriage Act, 1872 (Sections-6 and 9) and (iv) the Special Marriage Act, 1954 (Section-3). Pursuant to the judgement of the Hon-ble Supreme Court in *Seema v. Ashwani Kumar*¹³, the Odisha Hindu Marriage Registration Rules, 1960 and the Odisha Mohammedan Marriages & Divorces Registration Rules, 1976 were amended in the year 2006 and registration of marriages of Hindu and Muslim religions are compulsory since then.

- (v) In Goa, the process of registration of marriage with the State Government is initiated before its solemnisation under religious rites and ceremonies of the parties to the marriage. The position of registration of marriage in the State of Goa is progressive in view of the fact that it is governed under Civil Registration Code of 1912 which is mostly based on the Portuguese Code of 1867. The said Act is applicable to Daman & Diu as well. Even marriage of Roman Catholics solemnised under canonical law need to be routed through the Civil Registration Office. Marriage of Christian community could only to be solemnised by the Priest of the Church when No Objection Certificate from the Sub Registrar Office is produced before him. Article 1 of the Code of 1912 provides for compulsory registration to fix authenticity and juridical individuality of each citizen and to serve as basis of his civil rights. Article 4 thereof provides that no other mode of proof can be accepted. Article 6, thereof, provides that if lack of registration is attributable to an interested party, for proof, such party has to resort to judicial proceedings.
- (vi) In Puducherry, the Pondicherry Hindu Marriage (Registration) Rules, 1969 have come into force w.e.f. 7th April, 1969. All Sub-Registrars of Puducherry have been appointed under Section 6 of the Indian Registration Act, 1908 as Marriage Registrars for the purposes of registering marriages. In the Union territory of Puducherry, marriages of various communities are registered with the Local Bodies Authorities under Municipal/Commune Panchayat limits under the provisions of the Registration of Marriages by "Decree dated 24.04.1880 or under the Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 or the Special Marriage Act, 1954 by the Sub-Registrars of the Registration Department.¹⁰ Previously, the French Civil Code was used for registration of Births, Deaths and Marriages in the Local Bodies of the Union territory of Puducherry. The Registration of Births and Deaths Act, 1969 was implemented in March 1979 for registration of births and deaths. However, the Registration of Marriages is still under the said French Civil Code.
- (vii) In Jammu and Kashmir, as regards Muslims, Section 3 of the Jammu and Kashmir Muslim Marriages Registration Act, 1981 provides that marriage contracted between Muslims after the commencement of the Act shall be registered in the manner provided therein within 30 days from the date of conclusion of Nikah ceremony. However, the Act has not been enforced.
- (viii) So far as the Union territory of Chandigarh is concerned, the Hindu Marriage Registration Rules, 1966 have been framed.
- (ix) The Tripura Recording of Marriage Act, 2003 regulates compulsory recording of marriage solemnised under the Act updated by the Tripura Recording of Marriage (Amendment) Act, 2013.
- (x) Earlier there were other laws that existed for the purpose of registration of marriages. They are: (1) The Bombay Registration of Marriages Act, 1953, In five States provisions had been made for voluntary registration of Muslim marriages. These are Assam, Bihar, West Bengal, Orissa and Meghalaya. The Assam Moslem Marriages and Divorce Registration Act, 1935; the Orissa

Muhammadan Marriages and Divorce Registration Act, 1949; and the Bengal Mohammedan Marriages and Divorce Registration Act, 1876 are the relevant statutes. Many of these have been repealed for replaced by new legal regimes.

B. Compulsory Registration of Marriages Rules :-

- Bihar Marriage Registration Rules, 2006 are with respect to the compulsory registration of marriages. The same are applicable to the marriages of all citizens of India solemnised in the State;
- Madhya Pradesh Compulsory Marriage Registration Rules, 2008 for all marriages solemnised in the State.
- The Kerala Registration of Marriages (Common) Rules, 2008. provides that all Marriages solemnised in the State shall compulsorily be registered irrespective of religion of the parties. The Rules are now being implemented through the Director of Panchayat, who is Chief Registrar of marriage.
- Compulsory Marriage Registration Rules, Chhattisgarh, 2006 makes marriage registration compulsory for all, irrespective of community or religion.

C. Acts /Rules are under process in some States and Union Territories :-

The other States and Union territories are also taking steps to make necessary law on the subject. The proposed draft of U.P. Compulsory Marriage Registration Rules, 2014 is under consideration of the Government. Some Union Territories, i.e. Union Territory of Andaman and Nicobar Islands have forwarded draft law to the Union Government. The Nagaland Registration of Marriage Bill, 2012 was deferred and again discussed in April, 2014 in the Nagaland Legislative Assembly.

Conclusions and Recommendations :- The merits of registration of marriages have been discussed at length earlier in the report. A large number of countries have made registration of marriages compulsory. In India, because of its size,

population and the sheer diversity of customary forms of marriages, it has often been canvassed that such an endeavour to register all marriages would be difficult. However, the difficulty in implementation does not overshadow the merits of such an enactment.

Once enacted, the amended law would enable better implementation of many other civil as well as criminal laws. It would provide citizens, not new rights but better enforcement of existing rights under various family laws that grant and provide to protect many rights of spouses within a marriage. Registration of a marriage under any of the prevailing marriage Acts e.g. the Indian Christian Marriages Act. 1872; the Kazis Act, 1880; the Anand Marriage Act, 1909; the Parsi Marriage and Divorce Act, 1936; the Sharia Application Act, 1937; Special Marriage Act, 1954; Hindu Marriage Act, 1955; any other custom or personal law relating to marriage will be acceptable and a separate standalone legislation may not be required so long as an amendment is made to the Births, Deaths Registration Act to include Marriages.

Under the scheme of the Constitution the power to make laws governing marriage and divorce falls under entry 5 of the Concurrent List.¹¹ In view of the provisions of article 254 of the Constitution any law enacted by a State, which is in force on the date of commencement of this Act (Bill of 2015), if not in consonance and in conformity with this Act (Bill) shall be void to that extent. This Bill will not be in derogation of any provision of any existing Act dealing with compulsory registration of marriages, provided the existing law provides for stringent consequences for non-registration of marriages or provides a better mechanism for such a registration.

This Bill would supplement the domain of family laws that already exist and is not aimed at removing, abolishing or amending specific religious/ cultural practices and laws that are accepted under personal laws prevailing in India. The subject of personal laws is wide and complex,

and this report is not aimed at creating conditions for introducing family law reforms except the simple procedural change that Compulsory Registration of Marriages will entail.

Since, entry 5 of the Concurrent List of the Seventh Schedule to the Constitution, contains most matters of family law, allowing for the States to legislate on these matters, the recommended Bill would only serve as a guiding principle which would apply across the country but specific amendments to the scheme can be added by the States bearing in mind that there may be more effective ways for such registration of marriages depending on the context and particularities of different States. These differences may merely be procedural and not substantive. The above proposals shall be in addition to the other existing laws and will not affect any rights recognised under any other law or custom.

The Registrar who is responsible for the registration of births and deaths shall be responsible for the registration of marriages as well. Clause 8 specifies the people who shall be eligible to submit information to the Registrar in order to register the marriage. The Amendment Bill should provide that if the Birth or Marriage or Death is not registered within the specified time limit, then the Registrar shall on the payment of a late fee, register the death or birth (a) within a period of 30 days (b) within one year, only with the written permission of the prescribed authority; and (c) after one year, only on an order of a First Class Magistrate. It provides for a penalty of Rs.5 per day in case of delay in registration of 'marriage without a reasonable cause'.

On line of the Punjab Compulsory Registration Act, 2012, a provision in the Central Act may be considered such that, the Registrar may also, suo-moto, or on notice, enter and register any marriage which takes place in his jurisdiction, or if either of the parties have a permanent residence therein, in the marriage register maintained under the Act, after calling

the parties concerned and ascertaining the facts which are required for such marriage to be registered.

If the Registrar finds that, any entry of a marriage in the register kept by him under this Act, is erroneous in form or substance or has been fraudulently and improperly got made, he may subject to such rules, as may be made by the State Government with respect to conditions on which and the circumstances in which, such entries may be corrected or cancelled, correct the error or cancel the entry by making a suitable entry in the margin, without any alteration of the original entry, and shall sign and attest such an entry, and also indicate the date of correction and/or cancellation so made. Provided that no such correction or alteration shall be made to the detriment of any person without giving him an opportunity of being heard.

A provision from the Delhi Act is also worth including in the Central legislation that, in case a marriage is solemnised in any country other than India, then the Registrar of marriage shall satisfy himself/ herself- (a) That the marriage has been solemnised in accordance with the laws of that country between parties of whom at least, one is a citizen of India; and, (b) That at the time of registration, the marriage satisfies all the conditions laid down in Section 4 of the Foreign Marriages Act, 1969 (33 of 1969).

Village Panchayats, local civil bodies and municipalities should create awareness so as to get register all marriages with the local administration compulsorily. Further, producing of marriage certificate should be made mandatory when anyone writing the name of spouse in any application; for getting any benefit on behalf of husband or wife; for making application to government departments; for getting benefits of any welfare schemes like agricultural loan, education loan etc. Also, a unified database that consists of birth, marriage and death records would allow easy tracing of records.

The Law Commission of India is of the opinion that compulsory registration of marriages is a necessary reform and recommends the amendment of the Registration of Births and Deaths Act, 1969 suitably to include compulsory registration of marriage as well within its scope so that existing administrative machinery is able to carry out registration. Further, for this purpose i.e. compulsory registration of marriages including births and deaths the Commission recommends adoption of complete automation process by using the process of paperless documentation so the greatest extent possible.

The Commission is in favour of retaining the provisions in the Registration of Birth and Death (Amendment) Bill, 2015 regarding (i) penalty of rupees five per day in case of non-registration of marriage without a reasonable cause; (ii) providing false information regarding the registration of marriage; and (iii) refusal to furnish certain information, such as name and address.

However, the penalty so imposed should be made with respect to specific date subject to a maximum of rupees one hundred keeping in view the prevailing conditions in our country.

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10. Section 17(1) of the Act reads: "Save as hereinafter expressly provided, every marriage contracted between Muslims after the commencement of this Act shall be registered, as hereinafter provided, immediately upon the conclusion of Nikah ceremony connected therewith." "
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Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Inflow in India

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Abstract :- Usually, FDI is defined as an investment involving the transfer of a vast set of assets, including financial capital, advanced technology, and know-how, better management practices, etc. Foreign Direct Investment is considered to be the prime mover of the faster economic growth of developing countries. It is also considered to be the prime mover of the faster economic growth of developing countries. FDI can have a dominant role in the host economy by offering access to new technology, management competence, and gainful employment and thus can raise the level of economic growth. It may be noted that a large number of factors that may promote growth and FDI are largely common and, therefore FDI and development may go together in promoting the economic welfare of a country. there are a number of empirical studies which show that FDI has contributed positively to the economic development of developing countries. Some of these studies have focused on the countries which are receiving an increasing amount of FDI. One of the most striking developments during the last two decades is the spectacular growth of FDI in the global economic landscape.

The purpose of the study is to analyze the long-run and short-run relationship between FDI inflows and its various determinants in India during the period 1978 – 2016. The study is based on the presumption that FDI inflows are partly affected by policy factors and macroeconomic aggregates. FDI has proved to stimulate economic growth and development in many countries. It not only promotes capital formation but also improves the equality of capital stock, in order to promote competitive markets developing nations must reduce restrictions on FDI. There is no dilemma in allowing FDI into the domestic sectors. However, this forces the other players in the market to invest or to use their resources efficiently in order to stay in the competition.

There is no doubt that government has a major role to play. The level and composition of FDI that should be allowed is a challenge that needs to be addressed. There could be policies that lose us to suffer from them. The present study will be one step forward to analyze the positives and favorable for the Indian economy.

Keywords :- Market Size, GDP, Globalization, Economic Growth & Sustainable Development.

Introduction :- FDI inflows are playing an important role in the growth and development of the developing economy. It includes in introduce income, output, and employment in the host countries. It is considered as a vehicle for industrial restructuring, better investment prospects, production, and trade in the recipient countries. This has resulted in an advancement of investment and economic growth in Japan, NIEs of Asia, Hong Kong, Republic of Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, and ASEAN-4 (Indonesia Malaysia Philippines, and Thailand). This has brought changes aggregates in the home and host countries have also led to significant changes in the FDI regime.

The 1990s has recorded a major shift in the FDI inflows among the developing economies annually from US\$ 23225 million during the 1980s to US\$134620 million during the 1990s and further to US\$ 385874 million during the 2000s. FDI inflows in the developing countries increased to US\$ 646030 million which is 37.0 % of the world FDI inflows in the year 2016. However, this inflow of FDI is uneven and is concentrated in a small group of countries. In the developing countries, developing Asia accounted for 68.5 % of FDI flows to the developing countries and 25.4 percent of the world FDI inflows in the year 2016 (UNCTAD, 2017). FDI inflows In India accounted for 6.9 % among the developing economies and 10.0 1% among the Asian developing economy is

in the year 2016. In India, the economic reform policy measure of July 1991 has accelerated the inflow of FDI over the 1980s and especially. It has increased much force during the process 1990s.

Determinants of FDI inflows :- FDI flows during a exceedingly in a very} country are being influenced by social-economic, political, and human factors. The economic factors embody economic stability, the prospectus of market growth, infrastructure availability, laws, financial gain tax, exemption from withholding taxes, possession rights, patent protection, and simple investment approvals. The Macro- structure policies particularly resource allocation, structure, and organizational policies also influence FDI inflows. FDI inflows in an economy also are determined by political economy conditions together with value per capita, GDP growth rate, monetary development, domestic worth level, interest rate, exchange rate, and openness within the country. Location and culture, efficiency, and profit also are found in FDI inflows. FDI flows within the countries of East and Southeast Asia are being driven by a unique set of things equivalent to innovation-driven in Hong- Kong and Taiwan, investment-driven in Singapore and Malaysia, and factor-driven in Thailand, Indonesia, and also the Philippines.

Literature Review :- The boom of FDI flows to developing countries since the early 1990s indicates that multinational enterprises have increasingly considered these host countries to be profitable investment locations. At the same time, various experts argue that the determinants of and motivations for FDI in developing countries have changed in the process of globalization. As a consequence, it would no longer be sufficient to offer promising markets in order to induce FDI inflows. Policymakers would face rather complex challenges in striving for locational attractiveness to FDI (Kokko 2002).

Apart from unilateral liberalization, successive rounds of multilateral trade liberalization have reduced the relevance of market access through FDI for many products

(UNCTAD 1998: 115). Recent studies also suggest that FDI is increasingly referred to by some industries to slice up the value chain and to outsource less human capital-intensive stages of the production process to lower income countries offering the relevant comparative advantages. In process to lower income countries offering the relevant comparative advantages.(Raphael et al., 1998)

There are numerous theoretical literature and empirical studies which have given conflicting result about the determinants of FDI inflows. Caves (1996), observed that there is an increasing demand on the part of the countries to attract FDI inflows due to its spillover effects to the maximization of output, transfer of Technology, know how, training of the personal, and access to international markets of FDI in a country. One of the most necessary channels through that intra-industry spillovers might occur is competition induced increase in productivity of the domestic firms. The newer and advanced technology needs investment in physical and human capital by the receiver so as to effectively use the technology. However, this forces the opposite players within the market to speculate or to use their resources efficiently in order to remain in the competition. The empirical analysis tends to recommend that the FDI flows, in general, show an increasing trend during the post-reform period. Furthermore, country-wise comparison of FDI inflow additionally indicates that FDI inflow into India has increased significantly as compared to other developing economies within the recent years. Thus, the study indicates that the FDI inflows into India responded positively to the liberalization measures introduced in the early 1990s.

Using seven explanatory variables (market size, trade openness, infrastructure, inflation, interest rate, research and development and human capital), the authors have tried to find the best fit model from the two models considered (fixed effect model and random effect model) with the help of Hausman test. Findings – Fixed effect estimation indicates that market size,

trade openness, interest rate and human capital yield significant coefficients in relation to FDI inflow for the panel of developing countries under study. The findings reveal that market size is the most significant determinant of FDI inflows. (Kumari et al., n.d.)

Objectives

- To test identify the key factors that affect the FDI inflows.
- To examine the sectoral composition of FDI.
- To test trends and growth of foreign direct investment in India.

Research Methodology :- we have examined the cross-state and cross-time behavior of growth, poverty, and inequality in India and tried to find out the approximate factors for the cross-state and cross-time variations in the incidence of income poverty for the period from 1978 – 2016 by using panel data technique. Our study is exclusively based on the secondary data available from the various rounds of NSSO: reports of Planning Commission/NITI Aayog; Economic and political weekly (EPW) Research Foundation database, Reserve Bank of India on-line database; National Accounts Statistics; Census reports.

Model Specification, and Data, and Analysis :- The purpose of the study is to analyze the long-run and short-run relationship between FDI inflows and its various determinants in India during the period 1978 – 2016. The study is based on the presumption that FDI inflows are partly affected by policy factors and macroeconomic aggregates. The proposed study can be symbolically expressed as follows:

$$FDI f (Y, TO, DI, INF, EX)$$

In line with the available existing studies, this paper has made an attempt to investigate the linkage between FDI inflows and its various determining factors in the country. This can be expressed in equations.

$$FDI, \quad 1^Y_t, \quad 2^{TO}_t, \quad 3^{DI}_t, \quad 4^{INF}_t, \quad 5^{EX}_t, \quad \mu_t$$

.....

Equation (1)

$$\Delta FDI_t = y_{0+} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_1 \Delta FDI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_2 \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_3 \Delta TO_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_4 \Delta DI_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_5 \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_6 \Delta INF_{t-i}$$

$$+ \delta_1 FDI_{t-1} + \delta_2 Y_{t-1} + \delta_3 TO_{t-1} + \delta_4 DI_{t-1} + \delta_5 INF_{t-1} + \delta_6 EX_{t-1} + \mu_t$$

.....

Equation (2)

Hypothesis :- The null hypothesis of no Cointegration vectors among the variables in the model can be expressed as :

$$H_0: \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = \delta_6 = 0$$

Whereas, the alternative hypothesis is that-

$$H_1: \delta_1 \neq \delta_2 \neq \delta_3 \neq \delta_4 \neq \delta_5 \neq \delta_6 \neq 0$$

If the value of the F-statistic is found to be greater than the upper limit of the upper bound values proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001), we may reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables. If the values are lower than the lower bound values, we accept the null hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables in the model. If the values of the F-test lie within the critical bound limits then the outcomes will become inconclusive. There could be policies that lose us to suffer from them.

Empirical Analysis :- The study has employed the techniques to testing the unit root of time-series properties of data and the results are presented in this table the result shows that the variable is non-stationary at the level and stationery at the first difference:

Table 1: Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Variables	ADF Test		Significance Level		
	Level	Frist Diffrence	1 Percent	5 Percent	10 Percent
FDI	-1.387	-7.19	-3.621	-2.943	-2.61
Y	-5.515	-5.463	-3.633	-2.948	-2.613
TO	-0.781	5.052	-3.621	-2.943	-2.61
FI	-1.653	-5.058	-3.621	-2.943	-2.61
INF	-1.083	-6.187	-3.627	-2.946	-2.612
EX	-0.704	-4.638	-3.621	-2.943	-2.61

The result of Bound's test with two legs on the basis of set water Criterion are presented in this table:

Table 2: Bound Test result for Cointegration Relationship

Calculated F-Value:

Significance Level	Critical Bounds	
	Lower Bounds	Upper Bounds
1 Percent	2.08	3
5 Percent	2.62	3.79
10 Percent	3.41	4.68

This table presents the estimate of long run relationship among the variables in the model.

Table 3: Estimated Long - Run Coefficients for the ARDL Model

Dependent Variable: (FDI) Inflows

Variable	Coefficients	t-Statistic
Y	0.002	[1.787]
To	-0.013	[-4.602]
Di	0.015	[0.717]
Inf	0.065	[2.198]
Ex	0.015	[1.866]
Diagnostic Test		
Adjusted R Square	0.767	
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	0.551 (0.759)	
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation Test	0.198 (0.923)	
ARCH Test	1.322 90.268)	
Ramsay Reset Test	1.824 (0.089)	
Durbin Watson Test	1.95	

The constant of inflation is negative and important within the short run. The coefficients of the rate of exchange are positive in the short run. The outcomes reveal that sturdy economic science variables together with the past year performance of the macroeconomic aggregates are found to be a vital determinant of FDI inflows.

Conclusions and Suggestions :- This paper has applied the ARDL methodology to co-integration and ECM-based techniques to look at the cointegration relationship for the amount 1978-2016. The findings reveal that FDI inflows in the country are absolutely being influenced by value per capita growth, domestic investment, domestic indicator, and rate of exchange within the long-run. Within the short FDI inflows are absolutely influenced by the past level of FDI inflows, past level of value per capita, past level of trade openness, past level of domestic investment, and exchange rate in the country. The outcomes reveal that sturdy economic science variables together with the past year performance of the macroeconomic aggregates are found to be a vital determinant of FDI inflows. The current study is going to be one leap forward to research the positives and favorable for the Indian economy.

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Impact on Socio - Economic Condition of Women Police in Chennai

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Abstract :- This paper examines the analysis about socio - economic condition of women police in Chennai. This paper's main intention is to find out various aspects of socio - economic conditions impact on the development of society as well as police department which affects the various factors of women police like budget life, working hours, health care and lack of time for family responsibilities.

Introduction :- The position of women in India has been subjected to many modifications over the past few decades. They have an impact on of inequality is reflected in the status of female international in widely wide-spread and in India in particular. Over a period of time, famines engaged in number professions including police. The first Indian Police Service woman was recruited in the year 1973. The first batch of Women Police comprising one Sub-Inspector, and twenty Constables used to be recruited in 1973 and they have been connected to Chennai City Police. These Women Police in Tamil Nadu carried out site visitors and bandobust duties. Sometimes they assisted the Policemen in searching, interrogation and escorting ladies offenders. Some Women Police have been additionally utilized in frisking obligation at Air Port. In 1976, Women Police wings have been shaped every in Madurai, Coimbatore and Tiruchirapalli, with power of one Sub-Inspector, sixty Head Constables and six hundred Constables for augmenting the electricity of Women Police in Tamil Nadu. The work vicinity environment has a bearing on worker morale each positively and negatively. It influences their stage of motivation and performance.

Today, the police units are one of the most essential departments in India to defend the hobby of society and hold regulation and order. Women should equally study the positions in the department. The working prerequisites of the female constables mostly range in assessment to the working ladies in different departments.

Review of literature :-

Mangai Natarajan, (1996) examines that twenty-nine all-women police units have not a long ago (1994) been recognized by way of the Tamil Nadu State Police in South India. These chapters usually consist of 15 female constables and two sub-inspectors controlled by the command of an Inspector. They usually deal with family-related disputes and instances involving female and children, however also serve the full vary of normal police functions. The devices had been mounted for two major reasons: (i) to engender have confidence in the police amongst ladies victims and (ii) to furnish an independent profession shape for girls police officers. Interviews with officers in 5 of these gadgets printed a excessive degree of delight with the work and the profession prospects. Many more of the female in the gadgets than in a common pattern of females officers wondered in 1988 expressed hobby in performing the full vary of police duties, however they also said they would like to do this in devices staffed solely through women.

Vandana Kumari (1989) feels that, if a state is to develop, it is indispensable that

the fundamental standard of residing of the humans is elevated. This cannot be executed except female who constitute half of the countries improvement is taken care of and ladies have sufficient opportunities to be lively contributors in the improvement and end up marketers of alternate and beneficiaries at the equal time

Shamin Aleem (1991) The factors out the working stipulations of police women in India and she feels that the distribution of female police in that states is now not rational. She regrets that the annual reviews of the police branch do no longer point out about police have to be given independent powers and creditable jobs.

Ravindran Nair (1989) states that Women Police officers serve as social employees in uniform. He substantiates his opinion by using pointing out how Kiran Bedi. The First I.P.S officer in India has taken steps to rehabilitate households of convicts and has geared up de-addiction camps and for the drunkards. He feels that ladies can each love punish criminals and youngsters and change their activities.

Thompson, B. M., Kirk, A and Brown, D (2005) The study examines that the women police the fact which work stress influences policewomen's functioning in their household surroundings via a thing of burnout, emotional exhaustion. Role ambiguity and function overload have been regarded as work role stressors for assessment. It used to be observed that work primarily based aid from supervisors, however now not colleagues, used to be envisioned to decrease position stressors and emotional exhaustion, and enhance perceptions of household functioning.

Women police in India :- The function of the female police in India exhibits that female police have been basically made use of

to operate positive duties.

They encompass female police aid the Policemen when female and juvenile offenders are dealt with via Policemen; they are made use of in bandobust obligation the place girls in giant numbers collect for the duration of fairs, festivals, VIP visits and functions; they are made use of for escorting female suspects and offenders from Prisons to Courts; they are employed in lockup obligation when female suspects and offenders are stored in Police lockups; they are employed in frisking obligation at Airports; women police in Calcutta are made use of in public family members work; female police in Andhra Pradesh are made use of in site visitors manipulate and law work; women police in Karnataka are made use of as Receptionists in the Police Officers' Offices; women police in Delhi are made use of to operate a variety of obligations such as obligation Officers work, investigation of instances in opposition to women, Prime Minister's darshan duty, president's darshan obligation and frisking responsibility at Airport.

Women Police have to work round the clock. Hence, balancing the household responsibility with the obligation will be constantly traumatic to them.

The appreciation of society toward women police is special and at instances they are unwell treated. Due to the irregular working hours, infrequently get sufficient time to spend with their household members.

Some of the predominant problems and their motives in attaining wholesome work-life stability are mentioned in the following paragraphs.

Working Condition :- Women police face extreme issues due to bad and ineffective working conditions. There are insufficient welfare measures, insufficient facilities, unsure working

hours and leaves regulations make scenario worse. Work nature exposes them to criminals, deviants and anti-social elements. The nature of obligations in policing makes them work at atypical hours like late night time or early hours in the morning. Policing requires 24 hours obligation with no ordinary vacations and work schedule. This makes it very difficult for ladies to keep household duty alongside with the police work

Uncertain Role in Department :- Female police face a lot of uncertainty about their roles. By recruiting women's into the police pressure fully to have them work on aggressive behavior cases, and reasons associated to the household which restrict them to "cultural" roles, undermines their entire integration into the force. Role of female police is undermined and discriminated in task of responsibility through men police or superiors. Such discrimination and function ambiguity poses higher uncertainty and that affects each work and life.

Work-Life Imbalance :- Though twin duty of work and household have an effect on each guys and women, it impacts extra to ladies who are usually accountable for family chores, upbringing of kids, taking care of older household individuals and different dependents. Policing is regarded to be multifaceted occupation and consequently hanging a suited stability between the balance of work and household obligations is one of the largest challenges for ladies in the police.

Pleasure and Pains of Working Women :- The discomfort the shape of clash in performance the pair of roles falls closely of female who do no longer head, the family due to hierarchical social set up. Women's employment is approved, due to the fact it lessens monetary burden and raised quality of living. Performance of these two

roles effects in hassle to them. The situation spins into greater acute when working hours is no longer fixed

Indian Police Act of 1861 :- The Indian police act of 1861 was one of the two value recognized in the records of the police for the following reasons. In the first place, it had diagnosed the police of the total of British India and positioned them on a uniform basis. Secondly it has a characteristic with future and as such it shaped the ground work of future and as such it fashioned the foundation of the police icon in India even today. The Constitution of India has now not only granted equality to females however also empowered the State to undertake measures of effective discrimination in choose of female for neutralizing to cumulative, socio economic, academic rights, amongst different things, make certain equality earlier than law, equal safety of law, prohibits discrimination towards any citizen on grounds of religion, race, caste, intercourse or of start and ensures equality of probability to all residents in things touching on to employment. Articles 14, 15, 15(3), 16, 39(a), 39(c), and forty two of the charter are of precise significance in this regard.

Conclusion :- Women police normally face many troubles viz., non cooperation from the household for the home works, parenting, taking care of elders and children, friends and relatives. Even at administrative center too, they face troubles such as unhealthy workplace, misbehavior from male colleagues, use of vulgar language, non cooperation from the officers and colleagues. In this scenario household members' aid is a necessary issue in dealing with balancing work existence and family.

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Women' Self-Help Groups in the Pandemic of Covid-19 : Challenges and Impacts

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Abstract :- The COVID-19 crisis and the subsequent lockdown present one of a kind challenges for women's groups. However, past evidence recommends that women's groups may give individuals the components to adapt to the crisis. Lockdowns are especially challenging for women's groups on the grounds that practically the entirety of women's group members must meet. Considerably after lockdowns, social distancing strategies may restrain the capacity of ladies' gathering individuals to meet. Simultaneously, existing proof proposes that the social, human, and financial capital created through women's groups may empower women's groups to alleviate the effects of negative financial and well-being shock. Besides, rising evidence proposes that scaled-up self-help groups (SHGs) and reserve fund bunches have made administration structures that make these gatherings all around us situated to add to the execution of social security nets. Groups with wide populace inclusion, likewise, might have the option to help with general wellbeing anticipation measures. Consequently, the Indian government and nongovernmental associations with attention to India are diverting financing and network reaction activities through self-help and savings groups to restrain the negative monetary effects of the lockdown.

Keywords :- economic and social protection, Covid-19, women's self-help groups.

Introduction :- During COVID-19, it was perceived that the distance of the National Rural Livelihood Mission's ladies' self improvement gatherings, traversing the length and expansiveness of the nation, could be utilized to guarantee counteraction and regulation of the infection in rustic regions. Ladies' SHGs and their unified designs have huge potential due to the social

capital and fortitude organizations they have. This article presents experiences from an examination and sums up great practices, procedures, and developments that were led by SHGs in the midst of the pandemic. Discoveries from the report give early exercises from ground-level activity and proposals for fortifying the ladies' administration to react to emergencies.

The world over the effect of the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown has not been sexually unbiased (Gates 2020). Ladies have confronted extreme financial and wellbeing impacts, carried the lopsided weight of neglected work and remained powerless against sex-based brutality (UN 2020). By the way, in the midst of the troubling reality that the pandemic might turn around hard-battled gains in ladies' strengthening and sex fairness, an encouraging sign and motivation was given by the overlooked ladies who have been driving from the front in the COVID-19 reaction. This has been best exemplified in provincial India, where moving accounts of strength and development have risen out of ladies' self-improvement gatherings (SHGs) of the National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) supporting COVID-19 aid ventures.

Although ongoing reports center on the role of women's groups during the pandemic, there is for all intents and purposes on the impact of COVID-19 on the usage and viability of women's groups. Analysts have as of late began concentrating on the gendered effects of the pandemic, and strategy briefs hitherto have to a great extent fixated on the effect of intercessions with women under common conditions, perhaps in light of the fact that the crisis reaction has basically focused on prompt general wellbeing and social assurance reactions.

This concise intends to look at how women's groups might be influenced by—and may help moderate the impacts of—COVID-19 in India to distinguish possible chances and difficulties while remembering relevant contrasts across and inside nations. We led a fast survey of published evidence on groups' reactions to stuns, including evidence from wellbeing stuns and cataclysmic events. In like manner, we distinguished expected instruments through which women's groups might be influenced by COVID-19. We at that point consolidated evidence about these instruments with unmistakable insights on female populaces and women's groups in India. Likewise, we summed up developing, to a great extent episodic proof from reports about the role of women's groups in alleviating the outcomes of the pandemic.

Difficulties :- While SHG individuals started to lead the pack in emergency related creation and administration, there remain holes in information about the degree of financial advantages or compensation ladies got from these exercises, and regardless of whether this gave them relief, particularly when most other family pay sources were hit. While roused by a feeling of charitableness to serve their networks, more exploration is required into the individual cost taken on SHG ladies' well being and substantial uprightness from drawing in on the cutting edges, and how this was accommodated with the expanding weight of homegrown errands and care duties of youngsters, debilitated and older, incited by the lockdown. The working of SHGs was also affected, with bunches being limited from directing customary in-person gatherings of individuals in the underlying periods of the lockdown, and with challenges staying for bunch endurance from exhaustion of investment funds and hardships in collection of new reserve funds by individuals (Siwach et al 2020).

A new assessment of the National Rural Livelihoods Project (NRLP), led before COVID-19, uncovered that the program fundamentally affected women's family dynamics and dealing power (Kochar et al 2020). With an outside shock

like COVID-19, sex disparities for ladies and young ladies inside the family—in admittance to and utilization of qualifications like food and nourishment, human advancement information sources like schooling, command over assets and admittance to promising circumstances, and incorporating paid work openings with the arrival of male travelers to local towns—will probably heighten in the difficult occasions ahead (Tankha 2020a).

Inside NRLM, and even before the pandemic, disparities beset the SHG environment. For instance, imbalances in the limits of local area asset individuals and office carriers/individuals; in the fortitude of gatherings dependent on their development, length, and nature of assistance; in access and fair utilization of NRLM assets across individuals; and in admittance to and responsibility for, including monetary, property, and advanced resources of individuals. Over the long haul, these disparities—among individuals and among gatherings—may augment, further affecting admittance to credit, data, abilities, openings, privileges, and institutional entertainers, presenting difficulties for both intra-bunch attachment and gathering manageability.

Women's self-help groups (SHG) are fighting the COVID19 pandemic by ensuring that food reaches the most vulnerable during the COVID19 pandemic.

Fundamental administrations and sexual orientation-based brutality (Essential services and gender-based violence): The unprecedented conditions of the lockdown put into the spotlight worries about sex-based viciousness and women's wellbeing and prosperity. Reacting to

these heightened needs, engaged help was given to networks in areas where activities are being directed by the NRLM with specialized personnel.

Asset organizations Specifically, under the IWWAGE-upheld SWAYAM3 project, local area oversaw GRCs were set up, fully intent on aiding ladies to voice their interests, access rights and qualifications, and complaint redressal if there should arise an occurrence of viciousness. In Madhya Pradesh, an actual Lok Adhikar Kendra (sex equity focus) was set up in the Karhal and Sheopur squares of the Sheopur region with the help of the non-administrative association (NGO) ANANDI, while in Odisha, NGO accomplice Project Concern International dispatched a phone-based sexual orientation assistance focus giving tele-guiding administrations. In Bihar, Odisha, and Chhattisgarh, under the Swabhimaan Project being attempted in relationship with UNICEF and ROSHNI Center for Women's Collectives Led Social Action (CWCSAA), SHG ladies upheld cutting edge wellbeing laborers in the conveyance of antenatal and post pregnancy care and gave micronutrient supplementation to malnourished pregnant and lactating moms (PIB 2020b). In selected pockets of Odisha, cases were accounted for of SHG ladies going house to house to recognize pregnant and lactating moms and kids needing inoculation (Salve 2020).

Moreover, to guarantee the inventory of fundamental items for ladies and youngsters during the lockdown, the SHG ladies embraced the conveyance of sterile napkins (Asmita Plus) in Maharashtra, and Kudumbashree-worked units of Amrutham Nutrimix powder (wellbeing supplements for babies and kids) stayed functional in all areas of Kerala (Tankha 2020b).

We conclude the brief with certain experience of relevant elements to consider and confirm gaps to be addressed when planning women's group programming and exploration in the hour of COVID-19. In view of these experiences, we summed up an exploration plan that we intend to actualize as the Evidence Consortium on Women's Groups (ECWG). This

examination plan will concentrate on how COVID-19 and the related lockdowns may impact the work of women's groups.

The ECWG has recognized three ways in which the execution and viability of gatherings might be influenced by COVID-19 and reaction measures.

- Social distancing: Social distancing may expect gatherings to change their work—for instance, by constraining physical meetings and conceivably presenting virtual meetings and innovation.
- Economic stuns and social security: Economic stuns may reduce pay and reasonable market linkages for bunches connected to occupation advancement, which may eventually bring about gathering disintegration because of an absence of capital or ventures. Then again, gatherings may expand the versatility of their individuals through existing investment funds and gathering bolsters that can fill in as protection and social insurance.
- Coverage and existing administration structures of gatherings may boost governments and nongovernmental associations to give social wellbeing nets and assemble individual assurance gear through groups, which may build pay open doors for ladies' gathering individuals. Groups may likewise utilize their informal organizations for compelling health correspondence about COVID-19.

The probability and strength with which these three variables will influence groups will rely upon a few logical attributes, especially the seriousness of the lockdown and neighborhood pandemics. For instance, gatherings may even now have chances to meet in settings where lockdowns are moderately gentle or not carefully upheld.

Moreover, the capacity of groups to meet

carefully depends on women's access to cell phones and advanced education. Finally, governments are just liable to utilize women's groups to give social welfare nets or actualize different mediations where they work on an enormous scope.

Evidence on changes to usage of women's groups: Applying exercises from past stuns and the current condition

- **Social distancing** :- Evidence from the 2014 Ebola flare-up in Sierra Leone shows possibly destroying ramifications for bunches that can't meet. Enlightening information further recommends that, without money mixtures, ladies' obtain from casual channels expands and their capacity to take care of advances diminishes.

Under the current COVID-19 lockdown, women's groups in India no longer have physical gatherings. In India, the State Rural Livelihoods Missions (SRLMs) were prompted to suggest that SHG individuals ought to follow social separation while at the same time taking an interest in network reactions to COVID-19 through the creation of veils and defensive riggings and giving apportioned and prepared food to helpless families (Government of India, 2020). Currently, SHGs don't take part in ordinary exercises, for example, reserve funds, and advance dispensing or recuperation.

Previous evidence from Chile suggests that there is some extension to supplanting physical gatherings with instant messages. However, the potential for such methodologies profoundly relies upon access to cell phones, cash, and computerized proficiency. An investigation into the Feedback Message Experiment from Chile found that considering individuals responsible for basic criticism through instant messages rather than physical gatherings prompted an expansion in reserve funds. In spite of the fact that digitizing bunch activities could be an ideal arrangement in settings with high portable proprietorship among ladies and access to and utilization of versatile

cash, a comparative methodology may not be powerful in settings where openness and utilization of cell phones and cash are low.

Financial, wellbeing, and ecological stuns and social protection :- Women's groups, especially microfinance and business groups, can fortify individuals' strength against monetary stuns through utilization smoothing, improved access to resources, and encouraging social security benefits.

Evidence recommends that women's groups can give a wellbeing net to individuals whose salary streams have endured a noteworthy decrease because of catastrophic events. Although most examinations recommend that individuals from SHGs or investment fund gatherings can take advantage of reserve funds or access credit during emergencies, COVID-19 and the related end of monetary exercises may have longer-term suggestions on individuals' financial results. For instance, in India, information on SHG investment funds proposes that, in spite of the fact that individuals might have the option to depend on past reserve funds for the time being, the amassing of new reserve funds is probably going to be upset.

Conclusion :- The investigation has recognized exploration streams to consider the effect of COVID-19 on women's groups in India. In view of our underlying evaluation of existing examinations on past emergencies and the current reactions of ladies' gatherings to COVID-19 and the subsequent lockdown, we offer the following contemplations for policy makers who think about working with women's groups to convey social security and help with financial recuperation: Cell phone proprietorship and computerized education are significant elements to consider in building an advanced ladies' gathering reaction to the emergency. Networks are probably going to rehearse social removing for an unforeseeable measure of time, which may have extreme ramifications for bunches that meet much of the time to do most gathering capacities. Innovation may help keep bunches

practical. Be that as it may, many gathering capacities can't be conveyed electronically, especially in settings where cell phone proprietorship and advanced proficiency are low. Advanced gatherings, likewise, are likely less viable than physical gatherings in the age of social capital, including group solidarity and mental strengthening.

It is critical to arrange any reaction around the various sorts of women's groups and varying reactions to every unique circumstance. There is a wide variety in the execution of women's group programs and countrywide COVID-19-related strategies, just as inside nations. In spite of the fact that women's groups can add to versatility in the midst of emergencies by getting access to investment funds and credit, the probability of gathering individuals draining their reserve funds increments with the length of the lockdown. The salaries of casual laborers and ranchers may diminish because of overflow impacts brought about by the lockdown, constraining the capacity of women's group individuals to spare and gain pay. In certain unique circumstances, governments are as of now attempting to address this legitimately through financial safety efforts; for instance, by expanding the roof to guarantee free credits for SHGs in India. Be that as it may, such measures are not yet set up in settings where women's group work is of a smaller scope and is principally executed by nongovernmental elements.

There is a potential for coordinated effort between women's groups and the government, just as nongovernmental and private elements in the reaction to COVID-19. In numerous nations, women's groups effectively take part in conveying a network reaction to the pandemic and related approach stuns.

Women's groups can fortify their reactions by working together with nearby governments and private entertainers. The coordinated effort between SHGs, gram panchayats, and state governments in Kerala has likely contributed to alleviating the transient

negative outcomes of the emergency. Furthermore, captivating ladies' underway exercises when other market chains are being disturbed may prompt an open door for expertise advancement and arrangement of women's enterprises.

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Unemployment in India Due to Covid-19

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Abstract :- All developing country like India, are facing one major problem i.e. Unemployment. There are limited numbers of jobs in India and youth population is growing day by day. Here the condition of more demand and less supply, hence unemployment generated and the rate of generation are very fast like compound rate. There are high risk and uncertainty in agricultural and industrial sector. The increasing unemployment problem is definitely a serious for India. Without doing some efforts we cannot think of getting success in any field and this will also true for increasing population. We should handle the unemployment in such a manner that everyone gets a suitable job and help in increasing the growth of the country. Present study made an attempt to examine the penalty of joblessness following coronavirus induced lockdown on income and remittances of inter-state migrant labourers from Assam. The primary data for the study were collected through telephonic-based survey of 451 labourers during May-June 2020. The results of this study showed that, on an average, labourers in the study area remained jobless for nearly 2 months and incurred income loss of INR 28,955 thereby failed to send remittances towards their families by an amount of INR 12,215 during the reference period. As per the analysis of covariance the income loss and remittances unsent amount was higher amongst the elderly labourers engaged in professions which remained non-operational during lockdown period. Further, the additional days of joblessness increased their hardship in terms of income and remittances. With coronavirus being more than a health crisis, in short term it is necessary to minimise the loss of life, forwarding social and financial security for the families of migrant labourers and vulnerable sections for extended period of crisis, strategies for supporting agriculture and allied activities,

promotion of small and medium-size enterprises, imparting skill training for the unemployed and reverse migrant labourers, financial assistance for self-employment may be helpful. Suitable coordination of monetary and fiscal policy would be helpful for reducing the unemployment heading from the recessionary trend of the economy in the long run.

Keywords :- Unemployment, Population growth rate, Correlation and Regression, and Risk and Uncertainty

Introduction :- The population growth and employment growth of any country are necessary and important factors for economic development of the economy. All developing country like India, are facing one major problem i.e. Unemployment. In unemployment situation, people are willing to do a job as per their requirement and qualification but they could not be able to get it. There are limited numbers of jobs in India and youth population is growing day by day. Here the condition of more demand and less supply, hence unemployment generated and the rate of generation are very fast like compound rate. There are high risk and uncertainty in agricultural and industrial sector. So this lack of interest of people towards agricultural and industrial sectors leads the situation of unemployment also. Many people either attract towards same job or not attract towards any job. People who are suffering from the crisis of unemployment have to face various problems like physical and mental harassment and depression, social abuse, forced to choose or accept the wrong way of getting money in form of crime and violence, or sometime the hazardous results come in the form of suicide commitment by people due to being unemployed. This paper tries to attempt the search about causes, consequences and remedies of unemployment in India. "A man is unemployed

only when he is both without a job or not employed and also desires to be employed.” — Arthur Cecil Pigou.

Indian economy facing stagnation which means the unemployment and inflation belong same time. The cheap monetary and fiscal policy which is creates money supply and income of the country's people while the real GDP goes down, the reason for that like unproductive growth that is problem of our economy. The productive capacity of the economy down due to stagnation and excess capacity was increasing. The trade on between unemployment and inflation along with the sectors used high level modern technology machinery and excess labour force of the nation. The economy happened underemployment was nature in short run period but unemployment is very crucial problem for it. The famous British economist A. W. Phillips who first identified it, it expresses an inverse relationship between the rate of unemployment and the rate of increase in money wages (Real Income or Labour Productivity). The increase in labour productivity or real income, were equilibrium of demand and supply of labour. When equilibrium of demand and supply of labour is very low level of unemployment. The demand for labour depends upon labour productivity and wage rate and the supply of labour depends upon wage rate and population. When supply of labour excess over demand for labour condition of unemployment situation. The inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment rate as represented by Phillips curve is only a short - term relationship the factor which influences this inverse relationship between money wage rate and unemployment is the nature of business activity. In a period of rising business activity when unemployment falls with increasing demand for labour, the employers will bid up wages. Conversely in a period of falling business activity when demand for labour is decreasing and unemployment is rising, employers will be reluctant to grant wage increases. Rather, they will reduce wages. But workers and unions will be reluctant to accept wage cut during such periods. The Centre for Monitoring Indian

Economy (CMIE) has said. The Mumbai-based think tank said the rate of unemployment was the highest in the urban areas, which constitute the most number of the red zones due to the coronavirus cases, at 29.22%, as against 26.69% for the rural areas.

Hardest Hit Are Migrant Workers :- Hardest hit are migrant labours, nearly 70 per cent of the labour force lost their jobs, as far as auto manufacturing sector it may get worst because the demand likely to stay low and 55 per cent of employees, on contract who can be fired easily, as far as auto dealership is concerned, it became worse because labour is the 40 per cent of the dealer cost, hence, cutting jobs is easy way to cut cost.

The Urban Job Meltdown :- The fact that all salaried jobs put together account for just 21-22 per cent of total employment in India is worrying as it directly impacts a large share of private consumption.

“There are many more farmers than salaried jobs. And, there are even more daily wage labourers. Farmers and daily wage earners together account for nearly two-thirds of the Indian working population,” said CMIE. India lost 2.1 crore salaried jobs by the end of August, down from 8.6 crore in 2019-20 to 6.5 crore last month. “[Around] 21 million salaried job losses cannot be confined to only of the support staff among salaried employees. The damage is likely to be deeper, among industrial workers and also white collar workers,” the CMIE said.

Causes of Unemployment in India :- Though there are various factors that affecting the unemployment but some important factors which may be responsible for unemployment problem in India are as follows: 1. Backwardness and monsoon based agriculture in some regions and not reasonable price for agricultural produces. 2. Insufficient industrial development in India. 3. Migration of labour from rural area to urban area. 4. Emphasis on capital intensive technique. 5. Government policy towards private enterprises.

6. Population growth rate is high. 7. Defective and less practical educational system. 8. Slow growth of Indian economy. 9. Decline of medium and small scale industries and not suitable markets for its produce. 10. Lack of transparency in recruitment process.

Solution of Unemployment in India :- The increasing unemployment problem is definitely a serious for India. The solution may be finding out by doing some kind of efforts through government as well as responsible citizen of India. Without doing some efforts we cannot think of getting success in any field and this will also true for increasing population. We should handle the unemployment in such a manner that everyone gets a suitable job and help in increasing the growth of the country. Some important points may be given as follows:

1. Consider human being as a human and as a working unit. An employment is not necessary linked to a salary but a salary is necessary to keep the organization of a society in a good shape. We can work as artist, as a scientist, as a childcare person at home or at school etc. work should be a question of imagination and creativity. The financial system should change. A company that makes billions of profits should redistribute at least the sixty percent to this profit to the society.
2. Since the reasons of unemployment depends upon country to country and we cannot generalize it for all. It also depends on the policy of government. In certain country have over population while certain have less population. In general rather than depending on government jobs, training should be given or encourage in such a way to develop entrepreneur skills and innovations so that all be aware, how to tackle the solution and manage in their own.
3. Government should reduce interest rates so that more people can start and do their business, to promote small scale enterprises and grant entrepreneurs tax exemptions.
4. Government should increase their spending

or reduce the taxes etc. to create favorable business economic and job oriented market environment to reduce unemployment.

5. Highly qualified and highly skilled workers might travel and work in overseas countries that can offer better employment.
6. Educational institutions can teach students practical skills that will prepare them to be self employed, instead of seeking for paid jobs.

Unemployment and Inflation :- The unemployment rate is 2009 higher level indicate 3.75 per cent compare to other years, while the year of 2014 the unemployment rate is very low point of 3.41 per cent, the reason of huge level unemployment in 2009 to reflected US recession in 2008. Average inflation rate (%) in India increased by 12.11 per cent in period of 2010, then inflation rate is increased by 10.92 per cent at 2013 but decreased by 6.37 per cent in 2017. It was decreased continuously and reached to 2.49 per cent in 2017. In 2009 registered unemployment rate change in 0.21 per cent while same period inflation rate negatively 1.28 per cent. The years of 2014, 2015, 2016 the change in unemployment rate is negatively in respect of 0.08, 0.02 and 0.01 per cent when at the same time the year of 2014, 2015, 2016 the change in inflation rate positively like 0.49, 0.91 and 2.48 respectively, therefore trade-off between unemployment and inflation in Indian economy during short run. The pandemic has brought very uncertain times for employees. Resulting in that the stress levels are also hyped. One of the best tips to get them more engaged during the times of uncertainty is to teach them how to stay calm. Managing difficult situations is one of the best therapies to equip oneself with the power to fight it. Family communication channels should be channelised so that they can get family updates very easily in case of any emergency. More planning is required when employees are not working from the office. Keeping everything under control when half or more people are working from remote areas have a large number of challenges. These can be eased with the help of introducing a planning routine for everyone. A

15-minute session can help and give you a better understanding of where do you stand up. The team leader can take a quick session where all the updates, daily metrics, and the problems faced by the team can be talked about. It would help them to speak out about their experience while adopting a new module of work. Some fun activities can boost their energy levels. Engaging family and kids too can encourage involvement. A word of appreciation always works.

Conclusion :- The sudden outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has put the life on a standstill. All the sectors of life such as capital markets, aviation, tourism, retail, MSMEs, and many more. Due to the restrictions on international and internal mobility, there has been a decrease in the generated revenues which counted to be 9.2% of the GDP. The GDP growth rate has been adversely affected due to the lockdown imposed in the country. The aviation sector has fallen by as much as USD 1.56 billion. In March, oil plummeted to the biggest low in the past 18 years. It fell to as low as \$22 per barrel which then resulted in a withdrawal of USD 571.4 million by FPIs (Foreign Portfolio Investors). The huge decline in the revenues led to a decrease in global growth from 2.9% to 2.4%. The growth rate of the country went down to 3.1% for the fourth quarter of 2020 as per the statements given by the Ministry of Statistics (Dhamija, 2020) COVID-19 has been impacting all parts of life and employees have been facing various things from salary deductions to layoffs. Work from home is also a challenge for many. It a chaotic time for everyone no matter what level of the hierarchy it is, employees, managers, and leaders, and owners. Normalcy should be maintained like encouraging employees for their effortless work even during the tough times.

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